

The Chronos Effect

A New Look at Time

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Abstract:- What is time exactly? How does it work? Is it really the 4th dimension or something else? These are just some of the questions which we usually ask about it, where we could only have a very few or no answers to some other questions. Like would they know how time works? As there are now answers to specific measurements of many things, which probably includes the measurements of some time, the major question yet is on the true nature of time. This question was always what I ask myself after watching documentaries and reading Facebook posts in some science forums (since there are only limited forums which have active members on it).

Keywords:- Dark Energy, Spacetime, Multiverse, Quantum Entanglement.

I. INTRODUCTION

Please note that during when I made my theories, my knowledge of science was still at the year 2010, more or less. As this is just a few pages of research paper, I would not apply any divisions such as chapters and stuff. And after reading some sources, it had enlightened me, which is also why this research paper is already revised in a way. That these theories are already made simplified due to the authors character and for the readers as well, as well as the theories were made original.

I will mention that all this are just thought experiments using logic, imagination, and knowledge. Though some say that we have all the knowledge of time and what it is, I also think that we are only half way to solving what time really is, aside from the mathematical aspect of it. But I say, the answers are most times simple, which will be discussed right below.

II. ANALYSIS, DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

Lets start off with the very definition of time: "time is change, or the interval over which change occurs. It is impossible to know that time has passed unless something changes. The amount of time or change is calibrated by comparison with a standard."

Although it may not be possible to accurately measure all of time, and as some say that time is an illusion made by the brain or something, time is as real as it gets. Because if time wasnt even real, then why does the universe and all thats in it move forwards, and not just stay still? Why do all life move forward regardless if we believe time is an illusion and

if we believe that we literally made all reality through our brains? Thus regardless of whether we can measure all of time or not, or feel time through the changes around us or not, time is real and not just used for clocks to tell time. Even though time also has a special relationship with space, as both are relative to each other and indispensable.

I think that there are also 5 categories of time, where each tells on their roles in the universe:

- Universal time - where time flows and affects all universes or the multiverse.
- Cosmic time - where time flows throughout galaxies as they move around universes.
- Planetary time - where time flows through all planets and stars as they rotate or move around each galaxy.
- Material time - where its the time based on organisms and of all matter in the universe, where its divided into organic and non organic time. Where organic time refers to time from living organisms, and is much faster then the time for non organisms, such as all other things that arent living to begin with.
- Quantum time - where its the time at the quantum level, in which it involves the time of atoms and electrons.

Let us start at the very beginning of time, at the big bang, where time was very simple - to react or not to react. Where from my already explained "genesis theory": two simple atoms (positive and negative) will explode from the reaction from the compressed space in spacetime. Then from there, just like from the myth of Yggdrasil (the tree of life), spacetime slowly grew in entropy and matter expanded in time. Where spacetime then divides itself into branches of time, as entropy of matter ever grows within a given space. Time itself is both linear and dynamic, that time is linear only until a major decision takes place, and time becomes dynamic and branches out into multiple branches in spacetime. And thus, the multiverse is born, from all the branches of time that entropy has made within that space. But if that is so, what controls or manages spacetime and the multiverse? The answer is simple: dark energy. As there are no means yet of harnessing or measuring this kind energy, I can only hypothesize that dark energy is also like an Artificial Intelligence of sorts, where it can sort and manage all the data in the whole multiverse.

First of all, I will discuss from all the categories of time, about Quantum Time. As the name implies, its time at the quantum level, where time is either weird or not. As time at that level will depend on the random interactions of electrons and all the subatomic particles in all of space and time. And I

think that depending on the dark energy being generated, as like data, will determine the randomness of the interactions of all particles in spacetime.

Then we have material time, where it is the time for both organic and inorganic matter, which also determines the time for decay for any matter. Since as time goes by for all matter, some molecules or atoms that make up its skin would decay and fall off, thus shedding itself in time due to exposure of other elements or atoms as well. This type of time can be measured as well, unlike with quantum time. And this type of time is also affected by the planets time, in which the planet revolves or moves within a system.

Next is planetary time, where its the time a planet revolves around any system. There are many types of systems in space, wherein the type of planetary system will depend on how each planet and star were made at random during its creation. Wherein from the time it takes for matter to decay and shed some atoms or molecules, it will cycle itself within a system within the planets eco system. Planetary time, as it also involves the time of stars inside its system, would also depend on cosmic time as it circles around the galaxy.

Cosmic time, where its the time galaxies would circle or move around a given universe. Even though the name is cosmic, it doesnt mean that its the time for the whole universe. As cosmic time has similarities with planetary time, as both types move within a given system or pattern, they are basically different as well. Since galaxies carry very many planetary systems within just a galaxy. This type of time would depend on universal time as galaxies would move within a given universe only.

Last we have universal time, where its the time within the multiverse, as it will depend on the data managed by dark energy from the time of the big bang to the future time and in all universes.

Although those are the types of time within this and the multiverse, there are also things in this universe which we might take note. Such as: time in black holes, light speed, and quantum entanglement. Black holes, where I theorize that its a hole in spacetime which connects the multiverse, and where dark energy would pass through as well. And there is more, where the time inside a black hole is much like travelling beyond the speed of light and forwards towards another random timeline in a random space. Unlike with the speed of light, where you can move forwards in time towards a random time in the future. Then we have quantum entanglement, where its instantaneous communication of particles in two separate random places. And though there are many theories pertaining the end of time in our universe, aside from it having no basis except from the math, I think that time is eternal. Also, even though the beginning of time started with a big bang, begs the question: there must be something before it right? If not, everything wouldnt make sense. Well, I think there were 3 things at the beginning: space, time, and dark energy. Or else things wouldnt have been this balanced in the universe as we see now.

If time is real, then time travel is also real. Why? Because we all are already travelling through time, and towards the future. For each word of this paper, im even using some few second of my time in this timeline. Although the multiverse is real, there is also no clear way of telling if we have created another branch in time, aside from a very big decision which might change the world or something. And though some theorize or say that we decide our own future, which is somewhat true, its only true to this branch in time. Anyways, travelling towards the past wouldnt be possible, without probably destroying the current timeline and turning back all of time (which also includes universal time). And this feat would only require and be possible, with an enormously colossal amount of energy. In short, one would need to harness all of the energy in this universe, to turn back all of time. Though turning back time may not be possible without any sacrifices, going towards the future doesnt need any sacrifice, as it already sacrifices your present time for you to travel towards the future.

III. RECOMMENDATIONS

My recommendation is that the only way to know more about time is to logically analyze its true nature, as no present or maybe future equipment is able to analyze its true nature, where current science heavily relies on visible evidence and measurement for proof. As science is now almost at the limit of its capacity, as far as scientific and technological advances are concerned so far, the only things left to discover is for the final frontier which is space. And space as we know it is filled with Dark Energy and all other matter in the universe.

IV. CONCLUSION

“As the answer is simple, only the solution is complex, specially with humans”, that is the saying that I often told myself as it is the most logical approach to any given problem. These theories about the true nature of time is yet to be proven, yet it proves very logical and that the evidences are all around us, which we haven’t yet to realize. Please also note that this theory(ies) are maybe not yet complete and maybe still lacking.

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